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Two New Records of *Aspergillus* (*A. penicilloides* & *A. uvarum*) From Rhizospheric Soil of Potato Crops of Chichawatni, Pakistan

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Abstract

In this study two species of *Aspergillus* (*A. penicilloides* & *A. uvarum*) belonging to family Trichocomaceae of filamentous fungi have been isolated from rhizosphere soil of potato crops of Chichawatni. For isolation of fungi, culturing methods including direct plate method and dilution plate method on PDA medium have been used. After obtaining fungal cultures, species have been characterized, described, illustrated and identified on morphological basis. Morphological study included macroscopic and microscopic characterization of fungal taxa which are presented here as new records for Pakistan. Light micrographs of microscopic details of these taxa have also been provided.

Keywords: Culturing; Filamentous Fungi; Micrographs; New Record; Rhizosphere; Taxonomy

1. Introduction:

Pakistan has vast agricultural resources, fertile and well irrigated land, four different seasons and centuries old farming tradition of our forefathers. Due to these qualities, government attributed agriculture field is the major driver and carry central importance in Pakistan's economy (Noornai *et al.*, 2016). Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) is a significant crop of Pakistan due to its enormous use in our daily diet. Without potato vegetable basket of Pakistan is incomplete (Ahmad *et al.*, 1995). Soil fungal flora is an important component of soil because they contribute to form more biomass of soil than bacteria (Soni & Sharma, 2014). Some plants form mycorrhizal association with fungi that provide nutrients to plants by extracting from the soil (Ingham, 1976). But some fungi are pathogenic and have adverse effect on the diversity of plants. However, most of the fungi present in the soil act as decomposers and help in nutrient

recycling. The common methods used for the identification of soil-borne filamentous fungi are the colonies morphology and their microscopic characteristics. The identification method also depends upon the reproductive structures which are produced by fungi. But if the fungi do not produce morphologically distinct characters, then other identification methods are used like molecular DNA sequencing, which is the rapid detection and accurate identification method of fungi (Borman *et al.*, 2008).

In this investigation, two fungal taxa have been isolated from rhizospheric soil and identified on morphological basis and microscopic characterization. The isolated genus *Aspergillus* are anamorphic stages of the genus and belong to family Trichocomaceae, order Eurotiales, class Eurotiomycetes and division Ascomycota. These are the fungi with a high morphological and genetic variability (Thom & Raper,

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1951). They may exist as saprotrophs or facultative parasites and play significant roles in consumable and pharmaceutical industries. They are the causative agents behind diseases such as Aspergilloses etc. The Aspergilloses of the human respiratory system, skin, ears, sinuses, especially in patients with immunodeficiency or cystic fibrosis has already been reported caused by genus *Aspergillus* (Machowics-Matejko et al., 2014).

1.1. Objectives:

- To explore the diversity of soil inhabiting fungi, especially from rhizospheric soil of potato crop collected from different fields of Chichawatni by isolation through culture-dependent methods.
- To identify these fungi using macroscopic as well as microscopic methods.

2. Materials and Methods:

2.1. Sample Collection and Selection:

To collect soil samples, different potato field sites were selected and three to four replicates of soil samples were collected from each site. For isolation of filamentous fungi from rhizospheric soil, two culturing methods were used such as direct plate method & dilution plate method.

2.2. Sample Culturing:

PDA (Potato dextrose agar) was used as a nutrient medium (Murray et al., 2007) for growth of fungi. It was prepared by dissolving 39.0 g of potato dextrose agar powder in small amount of distilled water after that the volume of the solution was raised up to 1000 ml. About a temperature of 121°C was used to autoclave this medium. Approximately 25 ml molten cooled potato dextrose agar medium was taken and poured into petri-plates and it was allowed to solidify for about half an hour. In direct plate method, about 0.1 g soil samples were spread over the medium and rotated gently to spread soil particles on medium. In dilution plate method, 1 g soil of was dissolved in 100 ml distilled water to prepare 1% dilutions of each sample and 4-5 drops of dilution were poured on petri plates containing solidified PDA medium. Petri plates were then labeled, wrapped with parafilm and incubated at 25±2°C for seven days for obtaining fungal cultures (Kinsey et al., 2010).

2.3. Morphological & Anatomical Study:

In order to obtain pure cultures, strains of

each colony from impure culture were transferred to previously prepared petri plates containing solidified PDA media. Slide technique was used to identify the growing cultures anatomically. For slide preparation, a very small amount of a pure fungal strain was transferred on to a glass slide containing two drops of lactic acid (for coloured structure) and trypan blue (for hyaline structure). The cover slip was then placed on the material in such a way as to prevent air bubbles from getting trapped underneath it. We noted the morphological and anatomical features of colonies developing on PDA medium. Micrographs were taken and illustrations were prepared. Isolated filamentous fungal taxa have been identified by comparing our descriptions with published literature and updated keys (Barnett & Hunter, 1986; Ahmad et al., 1997).

3. Results:

3.1. *Aspergillus penicilloides* sp., Revta Fac. Agron. Vet. Univ.nac. Ka plantan2(19):245(1896) (Figs. 1 & 2):

3.1.1. Macroscopic Characterization:

Colony morphology: Pure culture green with white boundaries on PDA (Potato Dextrose Agar), raised, small patches spread on whole plate, punctiform, unequal colonies, some circular or some irregular, colonies are very small in first week. Margins of colony are irregular, uneven, some were rounded. Texture granular, rough. Reverse of colony light brown color due to pigmentation, patches of irregular colonies were also present.

3.1.2 Microscopic Characterization:

Vegetative hyphae intermingled, hyaline, septate. Conidiophores hyaline to light green, arises from the substratum or from mycelial hyphae, septate, thick walled, uneven thickening of walls, branched, erect or bent, no aggregation of cytoplasmic content, possess one conidial head at terminus, 2-6 µm wide. Conidial head present at the tip of conidiophore, hyaline to light green, biseriate, having sub-globose to ellipsoidal vesicles on which metulae and phialides attach, 80-120 µm. Vesicles single or thick walled, hyaline, covered by phialides. Phialides hyaline to light brown, flask shaped. Conidia ellipsoidal to sub-globose, smooth, thick walled, present single or may attach in a group of two or more, 3- 4 µm in diameter. Hulle cells round, green to parrot green, attached with conidiophore or present alone.

3.2. *Aspergillus uvarum* G. Perrone, Varga & Kozak, *Int. J. Syst. Evol. Microbiol.* 58(4): 1036 (2008) (Figs. 3-5):

3.2.1. Macroscopic Characterization:

Colony morphology: Pure culture dark green on PDA, slightly raised, covered the whole plate, in form of patches, growth dense, color of colony remains same. Margins irregular. Texture rough. Reverse of colony shows no prominent color, wrinkled. Impure culture dark green, raised, in the form of small circular

patches, secretion in form of drops present on the top, reverse of impure colony shows dark brown color.

3.2.2. Microscopic characterization:

Conidiophore yellowish-brown, double walled, unbranched, erect, straight, bend, uniform, septate, having one conidial head at tip, 4-6 μm wide. Conidial head round, brown, globose vesicles, uniseriate, having phialides, 130-150 μm . Vesicles light yellowish-brown, globose to elliptical, single walled, covered by phialides, 25-30 μm . Phialides covered the entire vesicle, brown. Conidia light brown, globose to sub-globose, slightly ornamented, thick walled, 3-4 μm in diam.

Figure 1: A-I: Morphology of *Aspergillus penicilloides*. A. Pure culture. B. Reverse of pure colony. C. Light Micrograph of conidiophore attach with Hulle cells. D-F. Light Micrographs of conidial head. G. Light Micrograph of vesicle. H. Light Micrograph of hulle cells. I. Light Micrograph of conidia. Scale Bar: A&B= 1.4 cm. C= 10.5 μm . D= 18.5 μm . E & F= 13.0 μm . G= 26.5 μm . H= 18.5 μm . I= 10.5 μm .

Figure 2: A-D: Illustrations of microscopic features of *Aspergillus penicilloides*. A. Conidiophore with biserial conidial head. B. Vesicle. C. Conidia. D. Hülle cells. Scale Bar: A= 8.0 μm . B= 30 μm . C= 5.0 μm . D= 30 μm .

Figure 3: A-D: Colony morphology of *Aspergillus uvarum*. A. Pure culture. B. Reverse of pure colony. C. Impure culture. D. Reverse of impure colony. Scale Bar: A&B= 1.3 cm. C&D= 1.4 cm.

Figure 4: A-F: Light micrographs of microscopic features of *Aspergillus uvarum*. A & B. Uniseriate conidial head. C & D. Conidiophore with attached conidial head. E. Conidia. F. Phialides. Scale Bar: A= 17 µm. B= 22.5 µm. C= 17.5 µm. D= 23.5 µm. E= 7.0 µm. F= 15.5 µm.

Figure 5: A & B: Illustrations of microscopic features of *Aspergillus uvarum*. A. Conidial head with conidiophore. B. Conidia. Scale Bar: A= 29 μ m. B= 14 μ m.

4. Discussion:

In this study two species of genus *Aspergillus*, namely as *A. penicillioides* and *A. uvarum* have been isolated, characterized and identified on the basis of morphological characterization. The genus *Aspergillus* has significant value in pharmaceutical industries because they secrete biologically active compounds such as antibiotics and mycotoxins (Desgos *et al.*, 1970). Many species of *Aspergillus* act as pathogens which cause diseases and infection in human and plants.

Aspergillus penicilloides is characterized by hulle cells which are rounded, greenish, attach with hyaline to green, septate and erect or bent

conidiophore bearing sub-globose to ellipsoidal vesicle on its tip with metulae and phialides attached. Sub-globose, smooth and brown conidia are attached to the phialides in chains. Our identification was confirmed by the study carried out by Samson and Lustgraaf (1978). This taxon has not been previously reported from Pakistan and first time isolated from rhizospheric soil of potato crop. It is a new record for Pakistan.

Aspergillus uvarum is characterized by yellowish-brown, double walled, unbranched conidiophore bearing round, brown, uniseriate conidial head. Vesicles are light yellowish-brown, globose to elliptical with globose to sub-globose ornamented conidia attached. This identification was

confirmed and descriptions are consistent with the study of Perrone *et al.* (2008). This species was previously isolated from grapes in Europe (Perrone *et al.*, 2008) but has not been reported from Pakistan up till now. It is isolated first time from rhizospheric soil of potato soil and presented as new record for Pakistan.

5. Conclusion:

Based on this study two species of *Aspergillus* (*A. penicilloides* & *A. uvarum*) belonging to family Trichocomaceae of filamentous fungi have been isolated from rhizospheric soil of potato crops of Chichawatni, Punjab Pakistan by using culturing methods and presented here as new records of Pakistan

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